

Health profiling and community well-being assessment in the SKBB Community of Taguig

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This study assesses the health status and medical needs of the Samahang Kapit-Bisig sa Bayside (SKBB) community in Taguig through an integrated medical profiling initiative. Conducted as part of Centro Escolar University's (CEU) annual Integrated Medical Mission, the research aims to develop a comprehensive health support programme. Using a descriptive-quantitative design, data were collected on demographics, medical conditions, lifestyle, oral health, and psychological well-being. A total of 58 participants underwent voluntary medical check-ups and screenings. Results revealed common health issues including high cholesterol, hypertension, diabetes, and respiratory illnesses. Unhealthy lifestyle habits such as alcohol consumption, smoking, and poor diet were prevalent. Oral health assessments showed widespread dental decay and limited access to care. While psychological distress levels were low, concerns about memory loss and age-related conditions emerged. Based on these findings, an intervention programme is proposed, incorporating medical monitoring, nutritional counselling, dental services, and health education. The study highlights the value of academic-community partnerships in addressing public health needs and presents a replicable model for outreach in underserved communities.

Keywords: community health; health intervention; medical mission; public health; university outreach

Community health is a critical component of public health, focusing on preventive, promotive, and curative strategies that improve well-being and address disparities in healthcare access. Effective interventions require structured, data-driven approaches that prioritise accessibility and sustainability. Academic institutions play a crucial role in this domain by facilitating healthcare initiatives that bridge gaps in service provision, particularly for underserved populations. One such initiative is the Integrated Medical Mission conducted annually by Centro Escolar University (CEU) Makati, which provides essential medical services to communities with limited healthcare access. This study profiles the health status of the Samahang Kapit-Bisig sa Bayside (SKBB) community in Taguig, with the goal of developing a tailored health support programme based on empirical findings. Healthcare access remains a persistent challenge in low-income communities, often due to structural and socio-economic barriers. Jnaneswar (2020) identifies workforce shortages, logistical challenges, cultural constraints, and inadequate healthcare facility utilisation as key factors limiting health service accessibility. These issues disproportionately affect marginalised populations, delaying diagnoses and treatment. Recognising these challenges, CEU Makati has integrated health assessments into its community outreach efforts, ensuring that interventions are informed by real-time data on disease prevalence, lifestyle habits, and healthcare-seeking behaviour.

The SKBB community, located in Lower Bicutan, Taguig City, has been part of CEU Makati's Community Outreach Programme since 2015. Comprising 92 members, 76 households, and 125 families, it spans 2,200 square metres and faces multiple socio-economic challenges. A 2018 needs assessment survey identified several priority concerns, including livelihood, education, environmental sustainability, healthcare, peace and order, home life, recreational activities, and infrastructure development (Acampado & Valenzuela, 2018). Among these, healthcare emerged as a critical area requiring targeted intervention. In response, CEU Makati's Integrated Medical Mission has provided medical check-ups, lifestyle assessments, oral health screenings, and psychological evaluations to the community, aiming to establish a comprehensive healthcare framework.

This study examines key health indicators such as medical conditions, dietary habits, oral health, and psychological well-being to develop a health profile of SKBB residents. The objective is to generate empirical evidence that can guide sustainable health interventions tailored to the community's needs. By engaging healthcare professionals and academic researchers, the initiative seeks to create a data-driven framework for long-term health improvements.

The Community Extension Programme at CEU Makati plays an essential role in bridging healthcare gaps through interdisciplinary collaboration. The Integrated Medical Mission, a flagship project of this programme, brings together healthcare providers, educators, and local stakeholders to design and implement targeted interventions. This initiative aligns with the university's commitment to public service and social responsibility, reinforcing the role of academic institutions in addressing real-world healthcare challenges. Beyond service provision, the mission serves as a platform for experiential learning, allowing students and faculty to engage in hands-on public health work.

This research adopts a descriptive-quantitative approach to assess the health status of the SKBB community. Data collection includes medical screenings, lifestyle assessments, oral health evaluations, and psychological well-being surveys. The findings will inform a structured intervention programme designed to address the identified health concerns of the community. Beyond immediate healthcare interventions, this study contributes to a broader understanding of community health and the role of academic institutions in public health advocacy. The findings

provide valuable insights that can inform policy development, healthcare planning, and future community engagement projects. The study also underscores the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in tackling complex health challenges and promoting holistic well-being among underserved populations.

By examining the specific health challenges faced by SKBB residents, this study offers a framework for integrating medical monitoring, nutritional counselling, oral health education, psychological support, and lifestyle modification strategies into a sustainable intervention programme. While the study is based on voluntary participation, which may introduce selection bias, and is limited to a three-month follow-up period, the proposed health programme incorporates mechanisms for continuous monitoring and evaluation to ensure sustained impact. Through this research, CEU Makati aims to reinforce its commitment to community health development and public service. The findings will shape future outreach activities, ensuring that healthcare interventions remain responsive to the evolving needs of the SKBB community. The Integrated Medical Mission (Figure 1) illustrates the structured approach taken by CEU Makati in delivering healthcare services, from community health assessments to intervention planning and implementation. Rather than being a one-time healthcare initiative, this process ensures that medical missions are part of a sustainable, evidence-based approach to community health.

Figure 1
Process flow of the integrated medical missions

LITERATURE REVIEW

Integrated medical missions play a vital role in extending healthcare to underserved populations, often in collaboration with universities and academic institutions. These missions not only provide essential medical services but also serve as platforms for research and data collection. Wilkins (2025) emphasise that successful university-community engagement must be based on trust, reciprocity, and sustained interaction, moving beyond traditional outreach models towards long-term partnerships that actively involve communities in shaping healthcare interventions. This approach ensures that health programmes are not merely imposed but developed collaboratively to meet the specific needs of the population.

Higher education institutions have historically been key players in public health initiatives, yet budget constraints, shifting institutional priorities, and resource limitations have, in some cases, reduced their level of community engagement (Murray-Hanson & Sandmann, 2021). Despite these challenges, Magnaye and Ylagan (2021) highlight that university-led extension programmes are most effective when they integrate healthcare, education, and livelihood support, rather than focusing on short-term interventions. While projects such as environmental initiatives and crime prevention efforts have yielded mixed results, health services have shown greater long-term impact due to their direct effect on quality of life. Singh et al. (2024) further argue that universities have a responsibility to build community capacity and foster sustainable health initiatives, reinforcing their role as drivers of social responsibility and public health advocacy.

One of the critical aspects of healthcare delivery in community settings is the role of pharmacies in patient-centred care. Pharmacies often serve as the first point of access to healthcare, providing medication counselling, chronic disease management, and preventive care. Effective pharmacist–patient communication is essential for ensuring adherence to treatment regimens and improving health outcomes (Omboni et al., 2020). The emergence of drive-thru pharmacies and digital consultations has enhanced accessibility, particularly in urban areas, enabling more efficient pharmaceutical services (Padilla & Faller, 2022). However, despite these innovations, workplace stress among pharmacists remains a concern, with ongoing challenges in balancing professional responsibilities and personal well-being (Barakat & Sallam, 2025). Expanding pharmacists' roles within community-based healthcare models could improve service delivery, though Poot et al. (2019) note that clinical reasoning among pharmacists tends to be more structured when patients actively seek professional advice. According to Padilla and Faller (2022), pharmacists are also becoming increasingly involved in global health initiatives, contributing to policy development, research, and community-based interventions.

Community nursing is another essential pillar of public health, particularly in areas where access to medical professionals is limited. Filipino nursing practice is distinguished by its holistic, patient-centred approach, integrating clinical, humanistic, and relational aspects of care (Pascual et al., 2023). Flaubert et al. (2021) identify four key functions of community nurses: facilitating healthcare access, continuous learning, fostering community understanding, and adapting care delivery to home environments. Nurses in community settings often assume expanded roles, including formulating local health plans, implementing public health policies, and supporting rural health midwives, particularly in areas where medical doctors are scarce (MacKay et al., 2021). De Foo et al. (2025) emphasise that people-centred care models are fundamental to achieving sustainable community health outcomes, particularly in developing regions.

Oral health is often overlooked in public health planning, despite its direct impact on overall well-being (Relajo, 2018). Preventive dental care, particularly in low-income communities, is essential for reducing the burden of untreated dental conditions. Alfaro (2017) advocates for community-based oral health education that includes screenings, fluoride application, and atraumatic restorative treatments (ART). However, financial constraints, limited awareness, and workforce shortages remain significant barriers to accessing dental care. Lim (2019) highlights that charity dental clinics fill a critical gap, especially for complex cases that might otherwise be neglected. Long-term integration of oral health services into broader community health initiatives is necessary to ensure sustained improvements.

Mental health also plays a crucial role in community well-being, with social support systems significantly influencing psychological outcomes. Kloos et al. (2012) describes community psychology as inherently collaborative, emphasising the importance of partnerships between researchers, local leaders, and residents in designing effective mental health interventions. Social bonds are a key determinant of psychological well-being, with Kagan et al. (2019) arguing that mental health frameworks should prioritise community-based interventions over individual-focused treatments. Pantea et al. (2021) identify four critical factors in social innovation for mental health: opportunity creation, innovative practice, capacity building, and value generation. These elements contribute to long-term societal impact by fostering inclusive, community-driven solutions that address psychological distress.

Nutrition is another fundamental aspect of public health, particularly in addressing diet-related chronic diseases such as obesity, diabetes, and cardiovascular conditions. Effective community nutrition programmes rely on education, dietary planning, and access to food resources. Ortiz-Andrellucchi and Serra-Majem (2019) emphasises the need for nutrition literacy campaigns that inform individuals about healthy eating habits and disease prevention. Ensuring that communities have access to affordable, nutritious food is crucial in addressing health disparities. Sianec (2024) notes that community dietitians play a key role in designing targeted interventions, while Guasch-Ferré (2024) highlights the importance of nutritional surveillance to track dietary patterns and implement evidence-based policy interventions.

Taken together, these studies underscore the multidimensional nature of community health and the importance of integrated interventions that address medical, pharmaceutical, nursing, oral health, mental health, and nutritional concerns. Universities play a critical role in bridging healthcare gaps by leveraging interdisciplinary expertise and fostering long-term community partnerships. While short-term interventions such as medical missions provide immediate relief, sustainable community health development requires evidence-based, collaborative strategies that prioritise preventive care, education, and capacity building.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive-quantitative research design to systematically assess the health status of the SKBB community. The approach allows for the collection of numerical data to identify patterns in medical conditions, lifestyle behaviours, oral health status, and psychological well-being. A survey-based method was used, ensuring a structured and replicable approach to data gathering.

The study population consists of 58 respondents, who were identified and recruited with the assistance of barangay officials and local leaders. Participation was entirely voluntary, and all respondents underwent medical assessments and surveys conducted by trained health volunteers during the Integrated Medical Mission.

A structured survey questionnaire served as the primary data collection tool, covering four key areas: general medical profile, lifestyle habits, oral health status, and psychological well-being. The questionnaire was adapted from previously validated instruments to ensure reliability and consistency. The dietary assessment component was based on the Fat and Fiber Questionnaire, which has a reliability score of 0.87. Psychological well-being was measured using the Level of Agony Questionnaire, as developed in the study of Pilao et al. (2017) on wellness and quality of life among the elderly. Additionally, the assessment of lifestyle behaviours was adapted from the Food and Lifestyle Questionnaire, originally designed for evaluating self-regulated development in relation to academic performance.

Data collection was conducted on 20 January 2024 and 16 March 2024 at SKBB, Lower Bicutan, Taguig, as part of the university's Integrated Medical Mission. Multiple departments collaborated to facilitate the process, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of community health.

To analyse the data, frequency and percentage distributions were used to describe demographic characteristics and medical profiles. Mean and standard deviation calculations were applied to assess food habits, lifestyle factors, oral health perceptions, and psychological distress levels. These statistical methods provided insights into prevalent health trends and risk factors, forming the basis for the proposed community health intervention programme.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the health assessment conducted on the 58 respondents from the SKBB community. The results are categorised into demographic and general medical profile, lifestyle and dietary habits, oral health status, and psychological well-being. The data provide an overview of the community's health status, risk factors, and prevalent medical conditions, forming the basis for the proposed health intervention programme. The findings are summarised in tables for clarity and ease of interpretation.

Table 1
Demographic characteristics and key medical indicators

Variable	Category	Frequency (n = 58)	Percentage (%)
Age	18–39	26	44.83%
	40 and above	32	55.17%
Gender	Female	39	67.24%
	Male	19	32.76%
Blood Sugar Level	Normal (<100 mg/dL)	21	77.80%
	High (≥100 mg/dL)	6	22.20%
Cholesterol Level	Normal (<200 mg/dL)	52	89.66%
	High (≥200 mg/dL)	6	10.34%
Blood Pressure	Normal (<120/80 mmHg)	25	43.10%
	Elevated (≥120/80 mmHg)	33	56.90%
Medication Intake	Yes	15	25.86%
	No	43	74.14%
Existing Medical Conditions	Hypertension	8	13.79%
	Diabetes	2	3.45%
	Respiratory issues	4	6.90%
	Arthritis	3	5.17%

Table 2
Key lifestyle factors, dietary habits, and oral health status

Variable	Category	Frequency (n=58)	Percentage (%)
Food Intake	1–2 meals per day	9	15.52%
	3 or more meals per day	49	84.48%
Physical Activity	Regular exercise (≥3x/week)	14	24.13%
	No regular exercise	44	75.87%
Smoking Status	Smoker	7	12.06%
	Non-smoker	51	87.94%
Alcohol Consumption	Drinks alcohol	16	27.58%
	Does not drink alcohol	42	72.41%
Dental Visits	Regular (every 6 months–1 year)	17	29.31%
	Only when in pain	41	70.68%
Common Dental Complaints	Toothache or cavities	32	55.18%
	Other issues (bleeding gums, etc.)	26	44.82%
Recent Dental Treatment	Received treatment (cleaning, extraction, filling)	30	51.72%
	No treatment received	28	48.28%

Table 1

Table 3
Demographic characteristics and key medical indicators

Variable	Category	Frequency (n = 58)	Percentage (%)
Physical Distress	None or Mild	42	72.41%
	Moderate to Severe	16	27.59%
Emotional Distress	None or Mild	39	67.24%
	Moderate to Severe	19	32.76%
Mental Distress	None or Mild	35	60.34%
	Moderate to Severe	23	39.66%

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the health status, lifestyle behaviours, oral health, and psychological well-being of the SKBB community in Taguig. The results highlight the pressing need for targeted interventions, particularly in addressing chronic health conditions, lifestyle risk factors, and access to healthcare services. This section discusses the key findings in relation to existing literature, explores their implications, acknowledges study limitations, and offers recommendations for improving community health outcomes.

A significant proportion of the respondents were aged 40 and above, with a higher number of females than males. Health assessments indicated a high prevalence of elevated blood pressure, blood sugar, and cholesterol levels, suggesting that many individuals are at risk of developing cardiovascular diseases. These findings align with national health trends, where an increasing number of Filipinos are diagnosed with hypertension and other non-communicable diseases. The lack of physical activity further compounds these risks, as a sedentary lifestyle is known to contribute to poor cardiovascular health. The study also observed that a notable percentage of respondents consumed alcohol, although smoking prevalence was relatively low. These findings suggest that targeted lifestyle interventions should prioritise increasing physical activity and improving dietary habits to mitigate health risks.

Oral health was another area of concern, with more than half of the respondents reporting dental issues, yet seeking treatment only when experiencing pain. This reactive approach to dental care is consistent with findings from previous studies indicating that limited access to affordable dental services and lack of awareness about preventive care contribute to worsening oral health conditions over time. Addressing this gap requires integrating dental education into community health programmes, promoting regular dental check-ups, and making preventive services more accessible.

Psychological distress was also prevalent in the community, with a significant portion of respondents reporting moderate to severe emotional and mental distress. These findings support existing research suggesting that low-income communities face heightened mental health challenges due to socio-economic stressors. The absence of structured mental health services within the community exacerbates these issues, making it necessary to implement initiatives that offer psychosocial support, stress management education, and accessible counselling services. Embedding these

interventions within existing health outreach activities could help increase accessibility and encourage participation.

The results of this study highlight the need for community-based health screenings to ensure early detection and management of chronic diseases. Regular monitoring of blood pressure, blood sugar, and cholesterol levels could significantly reduce long-term health risks. Health education programmes focusing on nutrition and lifestyle modification should be implemented to improve overall well-being. The promotion of affordable and locally available healthy food options would encourage better dietary habits, while structured exercise sessions could support an increase in physical activity levels. Establishing safe public spaces where residents can engage in physical activity may also be beneficial.

The integration of preventive dental care into community health missions is crucial in addressing oral health concerns. Free or low-cost dental check-ups could improve oral health outcomes, particularly if combined with awareness campaigns that emphasise the importance of regular dental visits. These interventions should be supported by training barangay health workers in oral health promotion to enhance community-level education and advocacy efforts. The high prevalence of emotional and mental distress suggests the need for mental health and psychosocial support services. Establishing community-based counselling services and peer support groups could provide residents with strategies to manage stress and anxiety. Training barangay health workers in basic mental health first aid would further increase access to psychosocial support, especially for individuals who may not actively seek professional mental health care.

Despite the valuable contributions of this study, there are several limitations. The small sample size limits the generalisability of the findings, and future research should aim to include a larger and more diverse sample. The reliance on self-reported data introduces the possibility of recall bias, particularly in lifestyle-related responses such as smoking and alcohol consumption. Objective measures, such as biochemical tests for nutritional status and step tracking for physical activity, could enhance the accuracy of future studies. The cross-sectional nature of the study also limits the ability to assess long-term health trends. A longitudinal approach would provide deeper insights into the progression of health conditions over time and the effectiveness of interventions.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study underscore the urgent need for holistic health interventions that address chronic disease prevention, lifestyle modification, oral health education, and mental health support. By leveraging community-based approaches such as regular screenings, structured health education, and accessible healthcare services, significant improvements in health outcomes can be achieved. Sustained collaboration between academic institutions, healthcare professionals, and community stakeholders will be essential in ensuring that these interventions are both effective and sustainable.

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